

Monitoring of thermoset composites curing by SHM sensors

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Context: Control of the health state

Different methods for the control of structures:

→ **NDT methods** to control parts after the manufacturing step
Ex: thermography pulse, ultrasonic methods

lightning strikes
in UD composites detected by pulse
thermography

Out-of-planes in composites detected by
ultrasonic controls

→ **SHM methods:**

Embedment of sensors into the structure to monitor the health state and to trigger targeted maintenance operations

PZT sensors network on a stiffened panel

Lamb waves propagation in composites

Control of structure thermomechanical stresses by FBG

→ Opportunity of the composites: Embed **sensors into the core of the composite**

Embedment of sensors into the core of the composites

Mechanical influence of the FBG embedment into the core of a composite

Goals/advantages:

- Getting knowledge of material's core behaviour
- Monitoring health state of material from manufacturing step
- Freeing from bonding issues (bonding quality and repeatability, bonding aging...)
- Protection of sensors from environment conditions

Break of their integration:

- Resistance of sensors to manufacturing conditions (temperature, pressure...)
- Intrusiveness of sensors on composite properties

Embedment of a FBG into the core of a thermoset composite

Influence of the sensors debonding on their response

Definition of the system

Microscopic observation of the prepreg

Material of interest:

- Thermoset UD prepreg: **IMA/M21ev**
Thermoplastic nodules at the interfaces
Thickness ~ 185 μm, Vf ~ 56%

Used for aircraft wings: high strength and toughness

Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG):

- Optical sensor sensitive to temperatures and strains

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = K_T \cdot \Delta T + K_\epsilon \cdot \Delta\epsilon + K_P \cdot \Delta P$$

- Gauge length = 5mm
- Diameter = 250μm with acrylate coating, 125μm without coating

FBG operating principle schema

Characterisation of the prepreg curing kinetic (1/2)

Anisotherm characterisation by DSC

- Monitoring of the curing during heat phase of the prepreg
- Identification of the melting temperature of the TP nodules

Differential Scanning Calorimetry set-up

Heat rate: 5K/min

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{1}{\Delta H_{tot}} \int H(t) dt$$

- Characterisation with different heating rates: Shift to lower temperatures

Characterisation of the prepreg curing kinetic (2/2)

Identification of a curing kinetic law

- Selection of a Kamal-Sourour model $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2\alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n$ $k_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_{ai}}{RT}\right)$
- Identification of the model parameters by a Nelder-Mead minimisation method

A_1 (s ⁻¹)	A_2 (s ⁻¹)	E_{a1} (kJ/mol)	E_{a2} (kJ/mol)	m	n
46.5.106	255.7	100	53.2	0.29	1

Instrumentation of the manufacturing process

- VBO (*Vacuum-Bag-Only*) process: Pressure only applied by a vacuum bag → $P_{max} = 1\text{bar}$
- Heat set-up: heating plate → temperature gradient through the thickness
- Laminate: $[0]_8, 100 \times 100 \text{mm}^2$

Process conditions:

Instrumentation:

- **1 FBG in the core** of the laminate at half-thickness, oriented perpendicular to the carbon fibres
- **2 monitoring thermocouples:**
 - 1 in the core of the laminate at half-thickness
 - 1 on the top of the laminate

Lay-up for the curing monitoring

Preliminary results

Data monitored during the curing cycle:

- Evolutions of λ_B and temperatures (in the core and on the surface) throughout the cycle
- Need to take into account the effect of temperature on the sensor response
- Need to decouple temperature and strain effects

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = K_\varepsilon \cdot \Delta\varepsilon + K_T \cdot \Delta T$$

$$K_\varepsilon \sim 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ nm}/\mu\text{def}$$

[Demirel, 2009]

FBG calibration → Evolution of K_T with temperature

Raw data recorded during the curing cycle

Evolutions of temperature and strain during the curing cycle

Influence of process parameters on sensors responses

Evolution of curing parameters:

- Influence of 3 parameters: Heating rate, temperature of the plateau, plateau duration
- Good tests repeatability:
 - slight differences during the heating phase BUT similar behaviour at the plateau and during the cooling phase
- Strain variations between 6000 and 8000 μdef (in function of the curing conditions)

Study of curing phenomena

Different identified steps:

1: Before curing

Low adhesion of the FBG

2a: Start of curing

Compensation of thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage

2b: Important chemical shrinkage

2c: Stabilisation of the chemical shrinkage

3: Thermal shrinkage

Evolution of the chemical shrinkage (1/2)

Strains and curing cycle:

For different manufacturing conditions (at **every moment** of the cycle):

- Strains measured by the FBG
- Curing degree estimated by the Kamal-Sourour model

Nonlinearity between the cure degree and the chemical shrinkage

- **Threshold value** of the cure degree **around 0.5**

Evolution of the chemical shrinkage (2/2)

Study of the final chemical shrinkage:

For different manufacturing conditions (at the end of the plateau):

- Maximum chemical shrinkage considered
- Maximum curing degree estimated by the Kamal-Sourour model

Singular points: data dispersion and high chemical shrinkages

- Hyp: Influence of TP nodules melting ($T_{\text{plateau}} > T_{\text{m nodules}}$)

Conclusions and Perspectives

Conclusions:

- Reliable and repeatable monitoring of a thermoset composites curing by FBG
- Identification of the different curing phases
- Possibility to estimate the end of the curing from strains monitoring
- Establishment of the link between the chemical shrinkage and the curing degree (non-linear)

Influence of chemical shrinkage on the composite coefficient of thermal expansion

Perspectives:

- Improve the estimation of the curing degree from the strains measurement
- Study the influence of thermoplastic nodules melting on the strains measurement
 - Validation of this method on another thermoset prepreg
 - Impact of curing degree on composite properties

Thank you for your attention!

Any question?